

SUPPLEMENTARY INFORMATION

“To Be, or Not to Be”: Critical Assessment of the Use of α -Acoustic Diversity Indices to Evaluate the Richness and Abundance of Coastal Marine Fish Sounds

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This supplementary contains 1 supplementary figure, 14 supplementary tables and 10 supplementary equations.

Experimental data supporting the findings of this study are available in open access online. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7789403>

Figures

Figure S1 H values for three different abundances (20, 60 and 100 fish sounds min⁻¹) with the loudspeaker silent (in blue) and with the loudspeaker emitting 1, 2 or 3 different fish sound types (in orange). Each period of silence preceded a period with sounds.

Tables

Table S1 Abundance and sound type species richness of each sound stimuli file created.

		Sound type richness		
		Low: (1 sound type)	Medium: (2 sound types)	High: (3 sound types)
Abundance	Low: (20 sounds min ⁻¹)	#1 low/low	#2 low/medium	#3 low/high
	Medium: (60 sounds min ⁻¹)	#4 medium/low	#5 medium/medium	#6 medium/high
	High: (100 sounds min ⁻¹)	#7 high/low	#8 high/medium	#9 high/high

Table S2 Localization of sampling sites in the lagoon of Temae (Moorea, French Polynesia)

N°	Localisation
1	Near a colony of <i>Dascyllus trimaculatus</i> in a <i>Heteractis magnifica</i> sea anemone.
2	Near a colony of <i>Stegastes nigricans</i> in an <i>Acropora pulchra</i> reef.
3	At the basis of a <i>Porites rus</i> pinnacle inhabited by a colony of <i>Chromis viridis</i> .
4	Limit between a patch of sand and an <i>Acropora pulchra</i> reef inhabited by a colony of <i>Dascyllus aruanus</i> .
5	In an area with <i>Porites</i> sp., <i>Montipora</i> sp. and dead coral near the reef crest.

Table S3 Correlation coefficients and associated *P*-values between the ADI, abundance, and sound type richness in the controlled environment. Statistically significant *P*-values are in red. BY = Benjamini-Yekutieli.

The correlation between abundance and sound type richness was null.

Step (Hz)	Threshold (dB)	Correlation			Non-adjusted <i>P</i>		BY adjusted <i>P</i>	
		ρ	R	Both	Abundance	Richness	Abundance	Richness
Default		0.63	0.053	0.63	0.068	0.89	0.94	1
10	-10	-0.21	0.74	0.77	0.59	0.023	1	0.70
10	-25	0.21	0.63	0.67	0.59	0.068	1	0.94
10	-50	0.95	0.10	0.95	< 0.0001	0.79	0.0044	1
10	-75	-0.053	0.32	0.32	0.89	0.41	1	1
50	-10	-0.10	0.68	0.69	0.79	0.042	1	0.94
50	-25	0.32	0.63	0.71	0.41	0.068	1	0.94
50	-50	0.95	0.10	0.95	< 0.0001	0.79	0.0044	1
50	-75	0.53	0.47	0.71	0.14	0.20	1	1
100	-10	-0.21	0.74	0.77	0.59	0.023	1	0.70
100	-25	0.21	0.63	0.67	0.59	0.068	1	0.94
100	-50	0.95	0.10	0.95	< 0.0001	0.79	0.0044	1
100	-75	-0.053	0.32	0.32	0.89	0.41	1	1
500	-10	0.32	0.59	0.67	0.40	0.095	1	1
500	-25	0.32	0.58	0.66	0.41	0.10	1	1
500	-50	0.95	0.26	0.98	< 0.0001	0.49	0.0044	1
500	-75	0.63	0.21	0.67	0.068	0.59	0.94	1
1000	-10	0.41	0.44	0.60	0.27	0.24	1	1
1000	-25	0.27	0.59	0.65	0.49	0.095	1	1
1000	-50	0.63	0.053	0.63	0.068	0.89	0.94	1
1000	-75	-0.054	0.19	0.20	0.89	0.63	1	1

Table S4 Correlation coefficients and associated *P*-values between the AEI, abundance, and sound type richness in the controlled environment. Statistically significant *P*-values are in red. BY = Benjamini-Yekutieli.

The correlation between abundance and sound type richness was null.

Step (Hz)	Threshold (dB)	Correlation			Non-adjusted <i>P</i>		BY adjusted <i>P</i>	
		ρ	R	R	Abundance	Richness	Abundance	Richness
Default		-0.63	-0.053	0.63	0.068	0.89	0.94	1
10	-10	0.10	-0.79	0.80	0.79	0.011	1	
10	-25	-0.21	-0.63	0.67	0.59	0.068	1	0.29
10	-50	-0.95	-0.16	0.96	< 0.0001	0.68	0.0044	0.94
10	-75	-0.58	-0.37	0.69	0.10	0.33	1	1
50	-10	0	-0.79	0.79	1	0.011	1	1
50	-25	-0.32	-0.63	0.71	0.41	0.068	1	0.29
50	-50	-0.95	-0.16	0.96	< 0.0001	0.68	0.0044	0.94
50	-75	-0.58	-0.37	0.69	0.10	0.33	1	1
100	-10	0.10	-0.79	0.80	0.79	0.011	1	1
100	-25	-0.21	-0.63	0.67	0.59	0.068	1	1
100	-50	-0.95	-0.16	0.96	< 0.0001	0.68	0.0044	1
100	-75	-0.58	-0.37	0.69	0.10	0.33	1	1
500	-10	-0.21	-0.54	0.58	0.58	0.14	1	1
500	-25	-0.32	-0.58	0.66	0.41	0.10	1	1
500	-50	-0.95	-0.26	0.98	< 0.0001	0.49	0.0044	1
500	-75	-0.68	-0.37	0.78	0.042	0.33	0.94	1
1000	-10	-0.41	-0.44	0.60	0.27	0.24	1	1
1000	-25	-0.27	-0.59	0.65	0.49	0.095	1	1
1000	-50	-0.63	-0.053	0.63	0.068	0.89	0.94	1
1000	-75	0.10	-0.26	0.28	0.79	0.49	1	1

Table S5 Correlation coefficients and associated *P*-values between α -acoustic indices, artificial (= introduced) abundance and artificial sound type species richness with *in situ* playbacks. Statistically significant *P*-values are in red. BY = Benjamini-Yekutieli. The correlation between abundance and sound type richness was null.

	Correlation			Non-adjusted <i>P</i>		BY adjusted <i>P</i>	
	ρ		R	Artificial Abundance	Artificial richness	Artificial Abundance	Artificial richness
	Artificial Abundance	Artificial richness	Both				
ACI	-0.41	0.14	0.44	0.0046	0.37	0.14	1
ADI_v1	0.13	0.25	0.28	0.40	0.098	1	1
ADI_v2	-0.12	0.18	0.21	0.45	0.24	1	1
AEI_v1	-0.15	-0.25	0.29	0.32	0.098	1	1
AEI_v2	0.14	-0.18	0.23	0.37	0.24	1	1
AR	-0.26	0.052	0.26	0.090	0.73	1	1
BI	0.16	0.11	0.19	0.30	0.48	1	1
GS	-0.31	0.25	0.40	0.040	0.10	0.61	1
H	-0.18	0.41	0.45	0.24	0.0053	1	0.14
M	0.82	-0.039	0.82	<.0001	0.80	<.0001	1
NDSI	-0.12	-0.31	0.33	0.45	0.042	1	0.61
NP	-0.47	0.098	0.48	0.0012	0.52	0.052	1
SE	-0.34	0.32	0.46	0.024	0.032	0.53	0.59
SPLpp_	0.019	-0.082	0.084	0.90	0.59	1	1
SPLrms_	-0.036	-0.0087	0.038	0.81	0.96	1	1
TE	0.82	0.22	0.85	<.0001	0.15	<.0001	1

Table S6 Correlation coefficients and associated *P*-values between α -acoustic indices, abundance, and sound type richness with *in situ* playbacks (delta sounds). Statistically significant *P*-values are in red. BY = Benjamini-Yekutieli. The correlation between abundance and sound type richness was null.

	Correlation			Non-adjusted <i>P</i>		BY adjusted <i>P</i>	
	ρ		R	Abundance	Richness	Abundance	Richness
	Abundance	Richness	Both				
ACI	-0.32	-0.0098	0.32	0.032	0.95	0.60	1
ADI_v1	0.048	0.19	0.20	0.75	0.20	1	1
ADI_v2	-0.034	0.16	0.17	0.83	0.28	1	1
AEI_v1	-0.10	-0.20	0.23	0.49	0.18	1	1
AEI_v2	0.0021	-0.16	0.16	0.99	0.29	1	1
AR	-0.072	0.0032	0.072	0.64	0.98	1	1
BI	0.16	0.11	0.19	0.31	0.48	1	1
GS	-0.37	0.27	0.46	0.012	0.077	0.50	1
H	-0.21	0.32	0.38	0.16	0.032	1	0.60
M	0.90	-0.032	0.90	<.0001	0.83	<.0001	1
NDSI	-0.19	-0.33	0.38	0.21	0.028	1	0.60
NP	-0.26	-0.095	0.27	0.089	0.53	1	1
SE	-0.36	0.31	0.47	0.016	0.040	0.53	0.64
SPLpp_	0.18	0.063	0.19	0.23	0.68	1	1
SPLrms_	0.13	-0.12	0.18	0.39	0.43	1	1
TE	0.45	0.11	0.47	0.0017	0.48	0.11	1

Table S7 Correlation coefficients and associated *P*-values between ADI, artificial (= introduced) abundance, and artificial sound type richness with *in situ* playbacks. Statistically significant *P*-values are in red. BY = Benjamini-Yekutieli. The correlation between abundance and sound type richness was null.

Step (Hz)	Threshold (dB)	Correlation			Non-adjusted <i>P</i>		BY adjusted <i>P</i>	
		Artificial Abundance	Artificial richness	R Both	Artificial Abundance	Artificial richness	Artificial Abundance	Artificial richness
Default		0.054	0.24	0.25	0.72	0.11	1	1
10	-10	-0.30	0.18	0.35	0.044	0.23	1	1
10	-25	-0.17	0.063	0.18	0.25	0.68	1	1
10	-50	0.13	0.24	0.27	0.39	0.11	1	1
10	-75	0.070	-0.032	0.077	0.65	0.83	1	1
50	-10	-0.20	0.21	0.29	0.19	0.17	1	1
50	-25	-0.16	0.073	0.18	0.29	0.63	1	1
50	-50	0.13	0.24	0.27	0.39	0.11	1	1
50	-75	0.033	-0.0062	0.033	0.83	0.97	1	1
100	-10	-0.30	0.18	0.35	0.043	0.23	1	1
100	-25	-0.17	0.063	0.18	0.25	0.68	1	1
100	-50	0.13	0.24	0.27	0.39	0.11	1	1
100	-75	0.070	-0.032	0.077	0.65	0.83	1	1
500	-10	0.027	0.064	0.070	0.86	0.68	1	1
500	-25	-0.12	0.18	0.21	0.45	0.24	1	1
500	-50	0.12	0.28	0.31	0.43	0.062	1	1
500	-75	0.050	0.043	0.066	0.74	0.78	1	1
1000	-10	-0.083	-0.18	0.20	0.59	0.24	1	1
1000	-25	-0.11	0.19	0.21	0.48	0.22	1	1
1000	-50	0.054	0.24	0.25	0.72	0.11	1	1
1000	-75	-0.30	0.18	0.35	0.86	0.98	1	1

Table S8 Correlation coefficients and associated *P*-values between ADI, abundance, and sound type richness per minute (natural + introduced) with *in situ* playbacks. Statistically significant *P*-values are in red. BY = Benjamini-Yekutieli. The correlation between abundance and sound type richness was almost null ($\rho = 0.045$).

Step (Hz)	Threshold (dB)	Correlation			Non-adjusted <i>P</i>		BY adjusted <i>P</i>	
		ρ	R	R	Abundance	Richness	Abundance	Richness
Default		0.25	0.19	0.30	0.10	0.22	1	1
10	-10	-0.37	-0.23	0.42	0.013	0.13	0.60	1
10	-25	-0.018	-0.32	0.32	0.90	0.033	1	0.85
10	-50	0.26	0.062	0.27	0.083	0.69	1	1
10	-75	0.11	-0.37	0.39	0.49	0.012	1	0.60
50	-10	-0.26	-0.14	0.28	0.089	0.37	1	1
50	-25	-0.033	-0.33	0.33	0.83	0.028	1	0.85
50	-50	0.26	0.063	0.27	0.079	0.68	1	1
50	-75	0.12	-0.24	0.27	0.44	0.12	1	1
100	-10	-0.37	-0.23	0.42	0.013	0.13	0.60	1
100	-25	-0.018	-0.32	0.32	0.90	0.033	1	0.85
100	-50	0.26	0.062	0.27	0.083	0.69	1	1
100	-75	0.11	-0.37	0.39	0.49	0.012	1	0.60
500	-10	-0.026	-0.27	0.27	0.87	0.078	1	1
500	-25	-0.081	-0.26	0.27	0.60	0.085	1	1
500	-50	0.24	0.10	0.26	0.10	0.51	1	1
500	-75	0.19	-0.052	0.20	0.21	0.74	1	1
1000	-10	-0.089	-0.10	0.13	0.57	0.50	1	1
1000	-25	-0.099	-0.11	0.14	0.52	0.47	1	1
1000	-50	0.25	0.19	0.30	0.10	0.22	1	1
1000	-75	0.25	0.25	0.35	0.10	0.099	1	1

Table S9 Correlation coefficients and associated *P*-values between ADI, abundance, and sound type richness with *in situ* playbacks (delta sounds). Statistically significant *P*-values are in red. BY = Benjamini-Yekutieli.

The correlation between abundance and sound type richness was null.

Step (Hz)	Threshold (dB)	Correlation			Non-adjusted <i>P</i>		BY adjusted <i>P</i>	
		ρ	R	Both	Abundance	Richness	Abundance	Richness
Default		-0.078	0.35	0.36	0.61	0.020	1	1
10	-10	-0.088	0.24	0.25	0.56	0.11	1	1
10	-25	-0.15	0.084	0.17	0.32	0.58	1	1
10	-50	0.042	0.18	0.18	0.78	0.24	1	1
10	-75	-0.16	0.0030	0.16	0.31	0.98	1	1
50	-10	0.0063	0.22	0.22	0.97	0.15	1	1
50	-25	-0.13	0.080	0.15	0.39	0.60	1	1
50	-50	0.046	0.18	0.19	0.76	0.22	1	1
50	-75	-0.19	0.051	0.20	0.22	0.75	1	1
100	-10	-0.088	0.24	0.25	0.56	0.11	1	1
100	-25	-0.15	0.084	0.17	0.32	0.58	1	1
100	-50	0.042	0.18	0.18	0.78	0.24	1	1
100	-75	-0.16	0.0030	0.16	0.31	0.98	1	1
500	-10	-0.052	0.16	0.17	0.74	0.28	1	1
500	-25	-0.034	0.16	0.17	0.83	0.28	1	1
500	-50	0.084	0.24	0.26	0.58	0.10	1	1
500	-75	-0.13	0.060	0.14	0.40	0.70	1	1
1000	-10	0.040	0.17	0.17	0.80	0.28	1	1
1000	-25	0.071	0.18	0.20	0.64	0.23	1	1
1000	-50	-0.078	0.35	0.36	0.61	0.020	1	1
1000	-75	-0.26	0.10	0.28	0.092	0.51	1	1

Table S10 Correlation coefficients and associated *P*-values between AEI, artificial (= introduced)

abundance, and artificial sound type richness with *in situ* playbacks. Statistically significant *P*-values are in red. BY = Benjamini-Yekutieli. The correlation between abundance and sound type richness was null.

Step (Hz)	Threshold (dB)	Correlation			Non-adjusted <i>P</i>		BY adjusted <i>P</i>	
		Artificial Abundance	Artificial richness	R Both	Artificial Abundance	Artificial richness	Artificial Abundance	Artificial richness
Default		-0.054	-0.24	0.25	0.72	0.11	1	1
10	-10	0.24	-0.16	0.29	0.12	0.29	1	1
10	-25	0.16	0.013	0.16	0.28	0.93	1	1
10	-50	-0.13	-0.25	0.28	0.39	0.10	1	1
10	-75	-0.055	0.0040	0.055	0.72	0.98	1	1
50	-10	0.16	-0.25	0.30	0.28	0.097	1	1
50	-25	0.14	-0.010	0.14	0.34	0.94	1	1
50	-50	-0.14	-0.25	0.29	0.35	0.098	1	1
50	-75	-0.019	-0.00040	0.019	0.90	1	1	1
100	-10	0.24	-0.16	0.29	0.12	0.29	1	1
100	-25	0.16	0.013	0.16	0.28	0.93	1	1
100	-50	-0.13	-0.25	0.28	0.39	0.10	1	1
100	-75	-0.055	0.0040	0.055	0.72	0.98	1	1
500	-10	-0.027	-0.054	0.060	0.86	0.73	1	1
500	-25	0.14	-0.18	0.28	0.37	0.24	1	1
500	-50	-0.15	-0.31	0.34	0.32	0.04	1	1
500	-75	0.022	-0.075	0.078	0.89	0.63	1	1
1000	-10	0.082	0.18	0.20	0.59	0.24	1	1
1000	-25	0.17	-0.20	0.26	0.28	0.20	1	1
1000	-50	-0.054	-0.24	0.25	0.72	0.11	1	1
1000	-75	0.029	-0.00010	0.029	0.85	1	1	1

Table S11 Correlation coefficients and associated *P*-values between AEI, abundance, and sound type richness per minute (natural + introduced) with *in situ* playbacks. Statistically significant *P*-values are in red. BY = Benjamini-Yekutieli. The correlation between abundance and sound type richness was almost null ($\rho = 0.045$).

Step (Hz)	Threshold (dB)	Correlation			Non-adjusted <i>P</i>		BY adjusted <i>P</i>	
		ρ	R	Both	Abundance	Richness	Abundance	Richness
Default		-0.25	-0.19	0.30	0.10	0.22	1	1
10	-10	0.28	0.15	0.31	0.069	0.34	1	1
10	-25	0.010	0.37	0.37	0.95	0.014	1	1
10	-50	-0.25	-0.071	0.26	0.093	0.64	1	1
10	-75	-0.16	0.21	0.27	0.29	0.17	1	1
50	-10	0.26	0.14	0.29	0.084	0.36	1	1
50	-25	0.020	0.37	0.37	0.90	0.012	1	1
50	-50	-0.26	-0.070	0.27	0.080	0.65	1	1
50	-75	-0.14	0.19	0.24	0.38	0.23	1	1
100	-10	0.28	0.15	0.31	0.069	0.34	1	1
100	-25	0.010	0.37	0.37	0.95	0.014	1	1
100	-50	-0.25	-0.071	0.26	0.093	0.64	1	1
100	-75	-0.16	0.21	0.27	0.29	0.17	1	1
500	-10	0.024	0.27	0.27	0.88	0.080	1	1
500	-25	0.093	0.25	0.26	0.55	0.11	1	1
500	-50	-0.25	-0.13	0.28	0.092	0.41	1	1
500	-75	-0.18	-0.32	0.36	0.24	0.034	1	1
1000	-10	0.089	0.10	0.13	0.57	0.49	1	1
1000	-25	0.19	0.11	0.22	0.22	0.48	1	1
1000	-50	-0.25	-0.19	0.30	0.10	0.22	1	1
1000	-75	-0.25	-0.24	0.34	0.11	0.11	1	1

Table S12 Correlation coefficients and associated *P*-values between AEI, abundance, and sound type richness with *in situ* playbacks (delta sounds). Statistically significant *P*-values are in red. BY = Benjamini-Yekutieli. The correlation between abundance and sound type richness was null.

Step (Hz)	Threshold (dB)	Correlation			Non-adjusted <i>P</i>		BY adjusted <i>P</i>	
		ρ	R	R	Abundance	Richness	Abundance	Richness
Default		0.013	-0.28	0.28	0.93	0.058	1	1
10	-10	-0.037	-0.15	0.16	0.81	0.32	1	1
10	-25	0.098	-0.098	0.14	0.52	0.52	1	1
10	-50	-0.090	-0.18	0.20	0.56	0.23	1	1
10	-75	0.16	-0.019	0.16	0.31	0.90	1	1
50	-10	-0.032	-0.18	0.19	0.84	0.24	1	1
50	-25	0.092	-0.12	0.15	0.55	0.42	1	1
50	-50	-0.096	-0.19	0.21	0.53	0.22	1	1
50	-75	0.16	-0.024	0.16	0.30	0.88	1	1
100	-10	-0.037	-0.15	0.16	0.81	0.32	1	1
100	-25	0.098	-0.098	0.14	0.52	0.52	1	1
100	-50	-0.090	-0.18	0.21	0.56	0.23	1	1
100	-75	0.16	-0.019	0.16	0.31	0.90	1	1
500	-10	0.047	-0.16	0.17	0.76	0.30	1	1
500	-25	0.0021	-0.16	0.16	0.99	0.29	1	1
500	-50	-0.11	-0.25	0.27	0.47	0.098	1	1
500	-75	0.021	-0.062	0.065	0.89	0.69	1	1
1000	-10	-0.12	-0.18	0.22	0.44	0.25	1	1
1000	-25	-0.090	-0.19	0.21	0.55	0.22	1	1
1000	-50	0.013	-0.28	0.28	0.93	0.058	1	1
1000	-75	0.26	-0.073	0.27	0.097	0.64	1	1

Table S13 Correlation coefficients and associated *P*-values between ADI, abundance, and sound type

richness in the natural environment. Statistically significant *P*-values are in red. BY = Benjamini-Yekutieli.

The correlation between abundance and sound type richness was almost null ($\rho = 0.53$).

Step (Hz)	Threshold (dB)	Correlation			Non-adjusted <i>P</i>		BY adjusted <i>P</i>	
		ρ	R		Abundance	Richness	Abundance	Richness
Default		-0.011	-0.37	0.43	0.91	<.0001	1	0.0019
10	-10	0.34	0.29	0.36	0.0003	0.0026	0.0045	0.031
10	-25	0.15	0.20	0.20	0.12	0.042	0.93	0.40
10	-50	-0.11	-0.50	0.53	0.26	<.0001	1	<.0001
10	-75	-0.12	-0.50	0.53	0.21	<.0001	1	<.0001
50	-10	0.33	0.25	0.34	0.0004	0.010	0.0056	0.11
50	-25	0.14	0.17	0.18	0.14	0.0867	1	0.75
50	-50	-0.068	-0.46	0.50	0.49	<.0001	1	<.0001
50	-75	-0.10	-0.51	0.55	0.28	<.0001	1	<.0001
100	-10	0.34	0.29	0.36	0.0003	0.0026	0.0045	0.031
100	-25	0.15	0.20	0.20	0.12	0.042	0.93	0.40
100	-50	-0.11	-0.50	0.53	0.26	<.0001	1	<.0001
100	-75	-0.12	-0.50	0.53	0.21	<.0001	1	<.0001
500	-10	0.17	0.054	0.18	0.073	0.58	0.66	1
500	-25	-0.018	0.10	0.14	0.85	0.28	1	1
500	-50	-0.055	-0.38	0.42	0.57	<.0001	1	0.0014
500	-75	0.059	-0.34	0.45	0.54	0.0003	1	0.0045
1000	-10	0.14	0.035	0.15	0.15	0.72	1	1
1000	-25	-0.15	0.045	0.22	0.12	0.65	0.93	1
1000	-50	-0.011	-0.37	0.43	0.91	<.0001	1	0.0019
1000	-75	-0.084	-0.27	0.27	0.39	0.0056	1	0.064

Table S14 Correlation coefficients and associated *P*-values between AEI, abundance, and sound type

richness in the natural environment. Statistically significant *P*-values are in red. BY = Benjamini-Yekutieli.

The correlation between abundance and sound type richness was almost null ($\rho = 0.53$).

Step (Hz)	Threshold (dB)	Correlation			Non-adjusted <i>P</i>		BY adjusted <i>P</i>	
		ρ	R	Both	Abundance	Richness	Abundance	Richness
Default		0.026	0.36	0.40	0.79	<.0001	1	0.0032
10	-10	-0.32	-0.27	0.34	0.00090	0.0052	0.012	0.059
10	-25	-0.12	-0.18	0.18	0.22	0.071	1	0.68
10	-50	0.049	0.42	0.47	0.62	<.0001	1	<.0001
10	-75	0.087	0.48	0.52	0.38	<.0001	1	<.0001
50	-10	-0.32	-0.27	0.34	0.00080	0.0061	0.012	0.065
50	-25	-0.12	-0.17	0.18	0.22	0.084	1	0.76
50	-50	0.053	0.43	0.47	0.59	<.0001	1	<.0001
50	-75	0.080	0.48	0.52	0.42	<.0001	1	<.0001
100	-10	-0.32	-0.27	0.34	0.00090	0.0052	0.012	0.059
100	-25	-0.12	-0.18	0.18	0.22	0.071	1	0.68
100	-50	0.049	0.42	0.47	0.62	<.0001	1	<.0001
100	-75	0.087	0.48	0.52	0.38	<.0001	1	<.0001
500	-10	-0.17	-0.057	0.17	0.090	0.57	0.78	1
500	-25	0.038	-0.085	0.13	0.70	0.40	1	1
500	-50	0.032	0.36	0.41	0.75	0.00020	1	0.0033
500	-75	-0.081	-0.51	0.56	0.42	<.0001	1	<.0001
1000	-10	-0.061	-0.0084	0.067	0.54	0.93	1	1
1000	-25	0.14	-0.046	0.21	0.14	0.64	1	1
1000	-50	-0.0097	0.36	0.43	0.92	0.00020	1	0.0033
1000	-75	0.15	0.50	0.51	0.14	<.0001	1	<.0001

EQUATIONS

$$M = \text{median}(a_i) \cdot 2^{1-d}$$

with $M \in [0, 1]$, a the amplitude envelope and d the digitization depth of the recording.

Equation S1

$$TE = - \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n a_i \cdot \log_2 a_i}{\log_2 n}$$

with $\sum_{i=1}^n a_i = 1$, $TE \in [0, 1]$, n the number of samples and a the amplitude envelope.

Equation S2

$$SE = \frac{-\sum_{i=1}^n f(i) \cdot \log_2 f_i}{\log_2(n)}$$

with $\sum_{i=1}^n f_i = 1$, $SE \in [0, 1]$, n the number of frequency bins and f = the mean spectrum computed using a Short Time Fourier Transform and then transformed into a probability mass function of length n .

Equation S3

$$GS = 1 - \sum_{i=1}^n f_i^2$$

with $\sum_{i=1}^n f_i = 1$, $GS \in [0, 1]$, n the number of frequency bins and f = the mean spectrum computed using a Short Time Fourier Transform and then transformed into a probability mass function of length n .

Equation S4

$$H = SE \cdot TE$$

with $H \in [0, 1]$, TE the temporal entropy and SE the spectral entropy.

Equation S5

$$AR = \frac{\text{rank}(M) \cdot \text{rank}(TE)}{n^2}$$

with $AR \in [0, 1]$, M the amplitude index and TE the temporal entropy.

Equation S6

$$ADI = \sum_{i=1}^S p_i \ln p_i$$

with p_i the fraction of sound in each i th frequency band in S number of frequency bands.

Equation S7

$$AEI = \frac{2 \sum_{i=1}^n i a_i}{n \sum_{i=1}^n a_i} - \frac{n+1}{n} \quad \text{with } a_i \leq a_{i+1}$$

Equation S8

$$ACI_{kji} = \sum_{i=1}^I \sum_{k=1}^K \sum_{j=1}^{J-1} \left(\frac{|a_{j+1} - a_j|}{\sum_{j=1}^J a_j} \right)_{ik}$$

with I the number of time frames, J the number of Fourier windows and K the number of frequencies computed along the signal

Equation S9

$$NDSI = \frac{(b-a)}{(b+a)} \quad \text{with } NDSI \in [-1, 1], a \text{ the anthropophony and } b \text{ the biophony.}$$

Equation S10